

Exploring the Use of Autoencoders in Particle Physics Data Compression

Malena Duroux

January 7, 2024

This project was conducted in collaboration with Samuel Hill

Abstract

This project involved an assessment of the usefulness of autoencoders for lossy data compression, for application in particle physics and beyond. How their design can be improved to better the quality of data reconstruction was also explored. The Baler collaboration's autoencoder-based software was applied to high energy physics, computational fluid dynamics, neutrino physics, and general machine learning datasets. Compression capabilities were assessed qualitatively by analyzing the differences between original and reconstructed data. The autoencoder was found to be very effective on the datasets the software was originally designed for, while performing poorly on image data with distinct lines as main features. The latent spaces of the autoencoder models were visualised to understand the shortcomings of performance, which were found to be a lack of classification capability and the use of a loss function that is not suited to what needs to be preserved in the data. Further improvements to the project are suggested.

1 Introduction

The natural sciences, physics in particular, are facing an ever growing data storage problem [1][2][3]. Some notable disciplines requiring large amounts of storage are Astrophysics [4] and Particle Physics [5], which are both using this data, in part, for the search of new physics. The High-Luminosity phase of the Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC), set to start operation in the coming decade, is expected to increase the recording of data at the LHC to a rate 7-10 times greater than the current one [6][3]. Data storage is not only costly, but also has an impact on the environment [7]. Many particle physics experiments are collaborations with members located all over the world [8] [9], who require data-sharing for their research.

There has been an increase in use of machine learning algorithms on experimental data and simulations [5]. Some machine learning (ML) algorithms can be used for data compression [4][10][1]. The search for new physics, for example in particle physics, implies the importance of retaining rare signals in background data [5][4]. ML algorithms have the potential for meeting these requirements, as they tailor their compression to the type of data they are used on. Baler is a data compression tool intended originally for the compression of data from high energy physics [11]. It has the potential to be applied to many different types of data in various disciplines. However, to realize this, rigorous testing on a variety of datasets is required for improvement of the software.

A pervasive problem in the field of ML is that there is limited understanding of how ML systems "reason" and how they come to decisions, for example about how to optimally compress data, often known as the black box issue [12]. Such understanding aids in improving the ML systems' effectiveness in compression.

The objective of this project is to test and increase the applicability of the Baler software, and to try and understand how the ML algorithm makes decisions on how to compress the data for best retention of data, to inform the direction for improving the software. Several aims follow. The first is to demonstrate the effectiveness of the Baler software on compressing high energy physics data, with the use of an example dataset from the LHC. A brief exploration of how the ML system represents the compressed data, is performed to try and understand the compression process. Baler is then tested on the compression of a simple image dataset, to demonstrate its versatility. This is followed by a neutrino physics image-based dataset to extend the application of Baler and highlight any shortcomings. The "black box" of the ML system is investigated to find out how decisions have been made and understand where shortcomings of the algorithm manifest themselves. This understanding can help point towards improvements. Finally, an artificial image dataset is used to assess the reliability of conclusions made about the ML system on the neutrino physics dataset exploration.

2 Theory

2.1 Machine Learning

2.1.1 Artificial Neural Network Structure

Artificial neural networks (ANNs or often NNs) are a type of machine learning structure. They are based on the brain, where neurons are connected in a complex web, communicating with one another via electrical or chemical signals [13]. Replicating this, an ANN is built up of several layers of nodes/neurons (artificial neurons). Each neuron takes an n-dimensional vector as its input, with some corresponding, predetermined "weights" for each vector dimension that determine the magnitude of contribution this signal will have, which is processed by being fed in (input) into a non-linear computation function, outputting a transformed scalar term that is passed on to the next neuron. The non-linear 'transformation' is called an activation function. It is the abstracted version of the "action potential" of its biological counterpart and introduces non-linearity into the NN. If the NN was linear, the entire network of nodes would merely behave the same as an individual neuron; the network output would be another linear activation function. Non-linearity allows the NN to capture complex patterns and relationships in the data.

Virtually any function can be used as an activation function, but some commonly used ones are the Sigmoid, Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU), and Leaky Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) functions detailed in Table 1. We can classify activation functions into saturating and non-saturating functions. An activation function is saturating if it plateaus on the extremes. The Sigmoid function is an example of a saturating activation function whereas ReLU is non-saturating. Nowadays, most NNs use non-saturating activation functions for two reasons: to solve the so-called "exploding/vanishing gradient" problem and to accelerate the convergence speed of the NN [14]. Leaky

ReLU is a modified ReLU with non-zero slope for negative x-values, introduced because ReLU's zero slope causes some units to never be activated, meaning they will not be optimised, as well as to further minimise the vanishing gradient problem [15].

Activation Function	Formula
Sigmoid	$f(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$
ReLU	$f(x) = \max(0, x)$
Leaky ReLU	$f(x) = \max(0.1x, x)$

Table 1: Some common activation functions. x is the input.

When many neurons are connected they form a NN. The NN is divided into individual layers of neurons, as seen in Figure 1 consisting of an input layer, into which the data is fed, followed by one or more hidden layers, responsible for non-linearly transforming the data and passing it on to the next layer, and finally an output layer, which transforms the data into a comprehensible output format. The specific architecture of the network, meaning how many hidden layers there are and how many neurons are in each layer, varies depending on the task it is designed for.

2.1.2 Training and Optimisation

Neural networks learn through training. A trained neural network is called a model. In the training process the weights of individual neurons get adjusted in order to minimise the discrepancy between the output predicted by the network and the desired output. Labelled examples are typically used during training. An example is a particular instance of data, \mathbf{x} (for example one image of a data-set containing 100 images). The label gives some sort of "definition" or "class" to the example. We use this labelled example to check whether the NN can accurately predict the label, indicating it is learning to predict correctly. This test is called validation. We can also have unlabeled examples, which we use after having trained our model on labelled examples, to predict new labels. To train the model we use an optimization algorithm to refine the weights. To measure the deviation of the model's predicted output from the desired output we use something called loss. In training, the goal is to minimise loss. Loss is customizable, but typically measured with some sort of error function. One iterates through all the examples, measuring this loss. The most common loss function to use is "squared loss", which uses a mean squared error (MSE) calculation [16]. Sometimes several loss functions are added together for a more effective total loss measure, depending on the type of model and what it is designed to do.

Before starting training, one initializes (meaning one picks) some random or trivial values for all the weights and the bias. Bias is a transformation term also found in the weighted input vector. For example, we can set both equal to zero. Then we run one iteration. The input is given to the input layer and passed through each consecutive layer, undergoing activation function transformations, eventually reaching the output and providing predictions. This whole process is called forward propagation. We then move on to what is called backpropagation. First, we compute the loss. Then, we compute parameter updates, meaning we generate new weight, \mathbf{w} , and bias, \mathbf{b} , values. We keep iterating until the model has reached suitable values, for which the loss is minimal, meaning the predictions are accurate. Usually, we iterate until the loss is steady for a certain amount of iterations. The number of iterations one runs is called the number of epochs that one trains for. Training for 100 epochs means iterating this process 100 times in a row.

Parameter updates are computed using gradient descent. Plotting the loss values for all possible weight values would roughly give a convex parabola. It is far too computationally intensive to compute every single loss for every weight and find the minimum value on the curve. But gradient descent informs whether an increase or decrease of weight value is needed to decrease the loss, by calculating the gradient of the curve at the point of the parabola where the weight value is located. If the gradient is negative w is on the left half of the parabola and needs to increase to minimise loss. Thus the model takes a 'step' towards the loss minimum value by increasing the weight value a step. The size that this step w is increased by is decided by a parameter called the learning rate. If you pick a learning rate that is too small, it will take too long to reach the loss minimum. But if you pick a too large learning rate, you risk overshooting the minimum. Learning rate is a hyperparameter, meaning one tunes it to optimise training. Since there are many weights, the gradient is a vector of partial derivatives with respect to \mathbf{w} .

Another important hyperparameter for training is batch size (BS). This is the number of examples used per epoch. With a data set of 70,000 examples, inputting all of these for each epoch will be inefficient and unnecessary. By setting a BS of say 6000, 6000 examples will be input

into the network for processing each epoch. Datasets are often also split into training and validation examples. The validation set will be used after each epoch, to test the networks ability for generalisation, meaning it's ability to work on previously unseen data.

2.1.3 Autoencoders

Autoencoders (AEs) are a specific type of NN, first introduced as a NN whose goal it is to reconstruct its input [17]. The unique feature is the constrained size of the middle layer, known as the latent layer or code. This layer contains a reduced number of nodes relative to the other layers, as seen in Figure 1, where the latent layer contains two neurons. The architecture (set up) of an autoencoder is symmetric. The input is gradually reduced to smaller size in the encoder section of the AE until the latent layer, after which, in the decoder, the number of neurons gradually starts increasing again, symmetric to the layers of the encoder. If we have an example which is an image of 28 by 28 pixels this would mean our "flattened" input vector has 784 dimensions, one for each pixel value, called a 784-dimensional input vector. The input layer matches one neuron to each dimension, giving 784 neurons. The encoder will gradually process this vector into smaller and smaller dimensions (fewer neurons), until the latent layer. The autoencoder maps each input, x , to an abstract latent point, z , of lower dimensionality in the latent space. The decoder then extrapolates z back to the same dimensions as the input, giving the output, \hat{x} .

Figure 1: Example structure of an autoencoder [18]. Each circle represents a neuron. X is the input vector and \hat{X} is the output vector. L_1 through L_5 are the layers of the NN, with L_3 being the latent layer.

A basic AE's goal is to be able to reconstruct its input as accurately as possible. With reference to figure 1, the goal is for $X = \hat{X}$. But because the AE has to push the data through the bottleneck (latent layer) where there is a reduced number of dimensions, it can't memorise the input in the form it is given. It contains too many dimensions. Essentially, the AE is forced to learn what it deems the most important features of the example (by weighting more heavily the vector components containing these) that it will be able to then accurately reconstruct the example from. It follows that one can also use AEs to compress data. The encoder acts as the compression process, the latent layer is the compressed information, and the decoder can perform the decompression. This is a form of lossy data compression, as not all information is preserved. The training is the most technologically intensive and time consuming part of the process. Once a trained model is obtained, one can apply the trained model to new, unseen data, similar to that the model was trained on, and it should be able to effectively compress and decompress the new data.

2.1.4 Latent Layer Visualisation

Looking at the distribution of embeddings (z values) in the latent layer is called visualising the "latent space" (LS) of the AE. Each point in the latent space represents the embedding of one example. Since it has the lowest number of dimensions, the latent layer is the easiest to visualize. We can understand the LS as a reduced dimensionality vector space containing the data that has been fit by our autoencoder. LS visualisations are most commonly used as a qualitative evaluation tool [19]. The specific goals of LS visualisation are highlighted by Liu et al. [19] through a literature survey. The goals which are relevant to this project are:

- *To understand the data.* Researchers use LSs to try and identify valuable relationships in the data. This helps in understanding the data and can lead to new discoveries.
- *Evaluate the model.* LSs can be used to compare and evaluate metrics and algorithms used for the model.
- *Explain the model.* Researchers look at the details of LSs to gain understanding, or at least intuition, of the model. This can be helpful in explaining the overall performance of the model and thus provide a direction to focus on for optimisation of model performance.

2.2 Relevant Particle Physics

2.2.1 Jets

In particle physics, jets are the complex signatures left behind by showers of quarks and gluons that strongly-interact [20]. They are collimated showers of particles produced from strong processes like proton-proton interactions. Looking at the substructure of a jet can help identify what type of particle created it. A dataset containing a jet thus contains important, detailed information about an interaction.

2.2.2 Neutrino Argon Interactions and Induced Particles

One of the datasets used in this experiment involves a Liquid Argon Time Projection Chamber (LArTPC). LArTPCs are detectors designed to study neutrino interactions and the products thereof. They consist of a box containing liquid argon, surrounded by anodes and cathodes. Neutrinos produced in particle accelerators reach the detector where they enter liquid argon. An interaction between Argon and a neutrino can produce various species of particles. When the particle, produced by the (ν, Ar) interaction, passes through argon, ionization electrons and scintillation light are produced along its trajectory. The scintillation light is detected by photomultiplier tubes after a few nanoseconds, providing a measure of time [21]. The ionization electrons are pushed towards the anode plate due to the constant electric field. After a few milliseconds they reach the anode, which is equipped with a grid of wire planes and charge sensitive readout planes. These wires pinpoint the locations of the electrons allowing recreation of the trajectories of the particle with this information, the time information from the scintillation light, and the velocity of the electrons. The result is an image whose y-axis is time-ticks and whose x-axis runs along the wires. It gives a 2D image of a 3D interaction.

The signals produced by neutrino induced particles in the Argon are typically characterised into tracks and showers (see [21] for examples). Showers are cascades of secondary particles. Electromagnetic showers are produced from photons, electrons, and positrons. Other particles will typically produce tracks, which appear as a single line, rather than producing further particles.

2.3 Dimensionality Reduction Tools

It will often not be possible to reduce an autoencoders latent layer down to two dimensions for direct, interpretable visualisation and also obtain a good reconstruction quality. Some further dimensionality reduction is required to visualise the latent layer in some format comprehensible to humans (2D or 3D). To make what goes on in machine learning understandable by reducing the content to 3D or 2D means the potential loss of important information about how the NN represents the data, in the form of loss of topology/structure/distribution of the data (e.g., how close points are to one another and if points with similar qualities are placed near each other). There are many dimensionality reduction tools that aim to preserve specific qualities in the higher dimensional data by using different transformations. These tools provide different "angles" to look at the LS from.

Most LS visualisations are either directly from a 2 dimensional LS, via Principal Component Analysis (PCA), via t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbour Embedding (t-SNE), or via custom projection tools [19] and consist of 2D scatter plots of the data. Below I briefly touch on the background of dimensionality reduction tools that are used.

2.3.1 Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [22] is a linear dimensionality reduction tool. It tries to capture the most variance possible [23]. The data is projected onto a new basis, consisting of

principal components. These principal components are found via an eigenvalue problem. A covariance matrix of the original dataset is found, where covariance measures how much two variables vary with each other. The eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the matrix are found. The eigenvalues represent the amount of variance capture by their eigenvector, thus, the largest one is the principal component. The eigenvectors are ranked by largest to smallest eigenvalues. For a reduction to 2 dimensions, we only look at the first two principal components. A detailed mathematical explanation can be found in Jolliffe and Cadima [23]. The main property of PCA in terms of data structures is that it preserves linear relationships, which most other dimensionality reduction tools (and AEs) don't do. Hence it is a valuable comparison.

2.3.2 t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbour Embedding

t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbour Embedding (t-SNE) [24], is a non-linear dimensionality reduction tool that focuses on capturing local structure in data. t-SNE uses probabilities, rather than covariance. The algorithm uses Kullback-Leibler divergence as a cost/loss function, which is minimised using gradient descent. The Kullback-Leibler divergence [25] heavily penalises the distance between nearby points. Thus, using it encourages tightly bound clusters. There is also a so-called perplexity term, which balances the emphasis on global and local structures. The combination of these two terms with t-SNEs nearest neighbour focus, means we obtain distinct, tightly bound clusters of similar points.

2.3.3 TriMap

TriMap [26] has a heavy focus on preserving the overall structure of the data it is reducing. The focus of TriMap is on triplet constraints rather than only nearest neighbour constraints. This means a comparison of the form "point i is closer to point j than point k ". TriMap first creates a low level embedding (low dimensionality visualisation) using PCA, and then modifies it using a set of triplets from the high-dimensional space. The algorithm also consists of a loss function, based on these triplets, which is optimised using gradient descent. TriMap was compared by its creators to both t-SNE and PCA and shown to be equally as computationally efficient as well as best at preserving the overall "qualities" of the original data (see [26] for details).

3 Methodology

3.1 Datasets Used

Several different datasets have been used in order to see how well Baler can perform on different data. The first two are datasets that are supplied with Baler "out of the box" (see Baler GitHub [11]).

3.1.1 High Energy Physics Data: Compacted Muon Solenoid

The first data set is from the Compacted Muon Solenoid (CMS) detector which sits at one of the four collision points of the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), where the energy of the particles gets transformed into mass, spraying many particles everywhere (into the CMS). CMS acts as a kind of camera, capturing the jets produced from the strong processes like proton-proton interaction in the LHC. The dataset is a subset of the jet data recorded by CMS in 2012 [27]. Each entry in the dataset is a proton-proton collision event and can contain multiple jets. The jets are represented as 4-vectors of (1) p_T , the momentum of the jet perpendicular to the collection of the colliding proton beams, (2) η , a quantity related to the angle between particle momentum and beam, (3) ϕ , the azimuthal angle measured around the beam, axis, and (4) m , the mass of the jet. These give the four momentum of the jets, (p_T, η, ϕ, m) . There are more associated variables but these four make up the most important variables for jet analysis at the LHC (see Appendix 2 in [11] for the full list). The entire dataset consists of 520,000 examples. The dataset is prepared such that each jet is contained separately.

3.1.2 Computational Fluid Dynamics

The second dataset is a simulated data set of computational fluid dynamics model used as a proof of principle, to test Baler's capability on image data and in other scientific fields. It simulates air flow, with the x-component velocity and comes installed with Baler. The dataset consists of slices

of a 3D space, thus 2D images, with velocity on the z-axis (indicated by the colour range of the image). There are a total of 60 images and the size of each image is 50 by 50 pixels.

3.1.3 Neutrino Physics Data: LArIAT

The third dataset comes from the Liquid Argon in a Test Beam (LArIAT) experiment at the Fermilab Test Beam Facility [8]. The LArIAT detector is a Liquid Argon Time Projection Chamber (LArTPC) placed in a tertiary low momentum beam of charged particles [8]. The interactions studied are between neutrinos at low momentum and Argon (neutrino energies are of a few GeV) [28] by looking at the particles produced as a result. The LArIAT LArTPC contains 170 litres of liquid argon and has dimensions of 47 cm (width), 40 cm (height), 90 cm (length, along beam axis) [28]. The dataset was shared by a member of the LArIAT collaboration [29]. The initial

Figure 2: LArIAT dataset. (a) Shows an example image of a positron from the LArIAT dataset with charge deposited shown on the colourbar. The x-axis is the time ticks and the y-axis is the wire number. (b) Shows the total charge of each event plotted against image number, with a key for the labels of the images. Note that the total charge is on a log scale.

dataset contained 150000 events, labelled by particle (e.g. "electrons minus event 1"). Each event only contains projections in 1 wire collection plane rather than both and the time axis has been transformed with a 21 time tick average, meaning the time axis contains less data than desired (the information over every 21 ticks has been averaged). The dataset also contained several empty events. Total charge in each event (each image) was plotted, as seen in Figure 2(b). A line of sparsity between 10^2 and 10^3 values on the y-axis was noted and the cutoff value of 400 was selected; all events below this value were removed, deemed as "empty" or not containing enough signal. This left 12640 images. 250 images of each particle type were selected, creating a dataset of 2500 images. This size was chosen such that it is manageable during training, without being too computationally intensive, as well as to limit the storage required on the computer used. The particle labels are: e^- , e^+ , K^- , K^+ , μ , *Michel*, γ , π^- , π^+ , π^0 , where all symbols have their typical meaning. Michel means a Michel electron, which is an electron that has been produced from a muon decaying at rest (see [21] for example image). The cleaning and pre-processing of the data was performed by Samuel Hill, my lab partner. Note that a shortcoming in using this dataset was the minimal description and information, thus these labels may not be intuitively logical and any inferences made about the physics in the data would need to be followed up on. But as the focus here is on compression and image reconstruction quality, this shouldn't impede the exploration greatly.

3.1.4 General Image Data: MNIST

The final dataset used is the MNIST dataset [30] (from the Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology database). MNIST is a database of handwritten digits and is one of the most commonly used for training image recognition and reconstruction models (see for example [26], [24]). The images are of size 28 x 28 pixels and each image has a corresponding label, to denote which digit it is (e.g. '9'). The total dataset has 70,000 images of digits from zero to nine. This dataset will be used to assess the effectiveness of Baler on general image compression.

3.2 Baler Model Design

The Baler software is used for conducting data compression. Baler uses the AE structure. It is a modular tool that consists of data pre-processing (where necessary), model architecture selection, training, compression, decompression, and reconstruction evaluation. The open source software is accessible on GitHub [11].

3.2.1 Input Data and Compression Metric

Before training is started, the data is flattened, for compatibility with PyTorch [31], the machine learning framework used in Baler. Baler accepts NumPy arrays as input as these are directly convertible into the tensors used by PyTorch.

Image data is not affected by flattening (no information is lost) as the 2-dimensional data is preserved in the tensor structure with the Dense AE described in Section 3.2.4. Baler has the functionality to split the dataset into inputs into training and validation sets itself, by specifying the ratio of data taken for validation to that taking for training. One can manually specify the `test_size` (size of the validation set) in the configurations before training.

The compression ratio (CR) is roughly the ratio of the latent layer size to the input size, as this is the compressed output and the input, respectively. The number of columns of data output corresponds to the number of nodes in the latent layer. The CR is defined as

$$R = \frac{\text{size}(\text{input file})}{\text{size}(\text{output file})} \quad (1)$$

but the actual CR has a slightly smaller ratio, as there is an output of auxiliary files along with the output file [11]. These files include auxiliary data such as encoder and decoder weights, biases, and any PyTorch data required for decompression. The actual CR is typically 2-7% smaller $R_{\text{actual}} \approx 0.9R$ (note, this is a rough approximation based on the findings in [11]). This is a negligible difference in HEP data.

3.2.2 Loss and Reconstruction Metrics

The total loss is defined as

$$L_{\text{total}} = (1 - \beta)L_{\text{reco}} + \beta L_{\text{sparse}} \quad (2)$$

where β is a hyperparameter which controls the contribution of each term to the total loss, called the regularization parameter. L_{reco} is the reconstruction loss (outlined in 2.1.2) and L_{sparse} is a regularization term. The L_{sparse} term helps avoid overfitting of the data, which is when the network fits the training data too well, such that it performs poorly on new, unseen data. Baler uses L_1 -type regularisation [32], which enforces sparsity in the weights of the AE. It is defined as

$$L_{\text{sparse}} = \sum_i |w_i| \quad (3)$$

where w_i is the weight value. To include this in the loss function is to penalise large overall weight values, meaning that some nodes will have low or zero weight values, i.e., sparsity. Removing unnecessary weights has also been shown to improve efficiency in HEP data compression [11]. The reconstruction loss for the Baler AE model is MSE loss defined as

$$L_{\text{reco}} = \text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^m \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \hat{X}_i)_j^2 \quad (4)$$

where m is the BS and n is the number of variables in each data entry. X is the vector of model inputs in that batch and \hat{X} is the vector with corresponding reconstructed model output. So L_{reco} is summed over each batch, giving the reconstruction loss for that epoch. We obtain a total loss value after each epoch to monitor how training is going.

3.2.3 AE and Reconstruction Metric for HEP Data

For HEP data such as CMS, Baler's HEP AE is used. This consists of 3 fully connected neural network layers (fully connected meaning all nodes are connected to all nodes in the consecutive layer). The encoder layers have 200, 100, and 50 nodes respectively, and the decoder mirrors these dimensions. Between the encoder and decoder, the latent layer dimensionality is determined by the CR, detailed in 3.2.1. If the CR is 5 and the input dimension is 100, then the latent dimension

will be 20. Baler uses Leaky ReLU as the activation function and the Adam optimizer [33]. This is still a gradient based optimizer, but it adapts learning rate based on the past gradient values as well as including momentum of past gradients, making minimisation faster.

The BS for the CMS dataset is 512, the learning rate is 0.001, and the regularization parameter, $\beta = 0.001$, for minimal but still helpful sparsity enforcement. Such a β value is sufficient for preventing overfitting and increasing efficiency in training. The learning rate is standard for an AE, and was demonstrated to efficiently minimise the loss for CMS without overshooting the minimum (see [11]). Due to limitations of computational power, the longest this model can be trained for is 500 epochs, as opposed to 1000 epochs as has originally been done (see [11]).

For performance evaluation on HEP data, residuals and response are used as metrics. They are defined as

$$residual = \hat{X} - X \quad (5)$$

$$response = \frac{residual}{X} \quad (6)$$

where X is the original data and \hat{X} is the reconstructed data.

3.2.4 AE for Image Data

The AE used for image data, originally designed for the CFD dataset, is almost the same as the regular AE. The layers are the same (200, 100, 50). The difference is that it takes 2D datasets.

The reconstruction metric for the image data is fairly qualitative. It consists of a difference plot, showing the differences between the original image and the reconstructed one. This is essentially a plot of the residuals, using Equation 5. Plotting the residuals as the image differences helps to understand what the model is learning from the images, and what it may be missing out, to help pinpoint any issues or point to how they could be resolved. The loss plotted against epochs is used as a metric for model performance. The validation loss in this plot is another useful reconstruction metric.

The specific training parameters for each dataset (BS, epochs, and, in some cases, learning rate) will be specified in the results.

3.3 Relevant Softwares Used

The implementation of Baler software is done following the ReadMe on the GitHub [11]. Datasets are all received in or made into `.npz` files to be compatible with Baler. PCA and t-SNE are implemented using Scikit Learn [34]. TriMap is installed through GitHub [26]. Datashader [35] is used for visualising large amounts of data and all figures are made using Matplotlib [36].

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Baler on CMS

Baler’s AE model was tested on the CMS dataset. The input shape of the data is [520000, 24]. The first training performed was 100 epochs long. After it was confirmed that everything was functioning as it should, one run of 300 epochs was done, and one of 500. The dataset was not split into validation and training. A more in-depth study of the effectiveness of Baler on this dataset has already been done [11], and thus it is used here mainly as a starting point to confirm Baler’s functionality and demonstrate ability of the AE on compression. β was set to 0.001, learning rate to 0.001, BS to 512, and CR to 1.6, as per the pre-set parameters (which have been optimised by the Baler Collaboration).

Due to limited computational power, however, the model could not be trained for more than 500 epochs. Even though the loss didn’t fully plateau, it did decrease by 3 orders of magnitude throughout training. The results from training for 500 epochs are shown in Table 2 and Figure 3, as this run portrayed somewhat better performance than that trained for 300 epochs, as expected.

The performance of Baler is measured by looking at the 4-momentum variable distributions, as well as their residual and response values. Whether to focus on residual or response values was decided by the dynamic range (DR) of the distribution. This is the difference between the maximum and the minimum value. As a rule of thumb, if this is between 0 and 10, we have a small DR and can focus on residuals. If the DR is larger, we focus on response since residuals may not

Variable	DR	Metric	Mean	RMS
p_T	48	Residual	-8.7×10^{-2}	4.5×10^{-1}
		Response (%)	-1.4	4.6
η	0.3	Residual	7.6×10^{-3}	9.7×10^{-3}
		Response (%)	2.0×10^{-2}	323
ϕ	0.3	Residual	4.7×10^{-4}	3.3×10^{-3}
		Response (%)	-1.0×10^{-1}	94
mass	9.0	Residual	-4.2×10^{-3}	6.1×10^{-2}
		Response (%)	28	21×10^4

Table 2: Residual and response mean and RMS values for 4-momentum variable distributions using the AE trained for 500 epochs. The values from suitable metric based on dynamic range is in indicated.

Figure 3: Histogram distributions of CMS 4-vector variables, after training the AE model for 500 epochs, along with either response or residual distribution (depending on dynamic range). "After" denotes the reconstructed data and "before" the original. A log scale was chosen in the cases where this helped the data be presented better.

provide us with the whole picture, due to having a larger overall distribution. This is highlighted in Table 2.

Mean and root mean square (RMS) values are used to judge the quality of residuals and response distributions. For a good reconstruction, the distributions would be centred around zero.

With reference to Figure 3, the variable distributions demonstrate a fairly accurate reconstruction quality, and this is largely reflected in mean residual/response values being close to zero (in Table 2). Note the large mean and RMS value for the mass response in Table 2. A DR of 9 means both residuals and response could be informative, although residuals have been chosen here since 9 is still fairly small. The mean response value is large, while the response values are mainly centred around zero in the distribution (not pictured here). When plotting residuals against mass value, it was found that a few points had values of ± 1000 , while most were around zero. These were considered outliers, which the model has failed to predict accurately. However, given the results in [11], this is something that could be fixed with longer training and a closer focus on optimisation of parameters. When looking closely at the mass variable distribution, one can see a bar created in the "after" that does not reflect a "before" at around 150 GeV. This is most likely the cause of the large mean and RMS.

Some brief considerations of LS visualisation were made for CMS trained AE. The LS is 15-dimensional. So the data shape has gone from $[520000, 24]$ to $[520000, 15]$. The first approach, to visualise the LS directly, was to compare all of the 15 dimensions (called components) one by one. Comparison plots for each dimension were made, some examples are shown in Figure 4. Some dimensions were found to contain linear distributions, like Figure 4c, or to have all data concentrated closely around zero, like Figure 4a. One could suggest that these dimensions have been made redundant, possibly due to the sparsity constraint on the loss function. This either means one could further reduce the compression, or one should put a lower sparsity constraint, in order to have the model learn more efficiently. In Wetzel [37], a Variational Autoencoder (VAE, a specific type of AE) trained on the two-dimensional Ising model was used to test whether one can observe phase transitions using machine learning. It was first only trained with a 1-dimensional LS. When a second dimension was added, it only slightly changed the results. It was concluded that

Figure 4: Examples of 1 by 1 component comparison of compressed CMS data. Comparisons shown are (a) 11 vs 5, concentrated around origin (b) 1 vs 3, showing non-linear shape (c) 4 vs 14, showing a fairly linear distributions of points. The density of points is shown by the darkness of the colour (the opacity). Dark blue is where the points are most concentrated.

the second dimension didn't add much, as it stayed close to zero in the LS distribution. A similar point could be made about component 5 in the CMS latent layer, where all points are concentrated around zero (see the example in Figure 4.a). If we are only focusing on the reconstruction of the 4-momentum vector components, we could try and reduce the dimensionality from 24 columns to 4 (i.e., a 4-dimensional LS). Trunz et al. [38] focus on making an informed decision on the dimensions of the LS. This is likened to PCA, in that we truncate our dimensions once we feel we have contained all the important information in the first k dimensions. The dimensions are ranked by using calculated "Shapley" values. This can be considered another conceptualisation of the sparsity constraint in the AE. However, instead of encouraging sparsity, one concludes that only the first k dimensions are important for a good balance between efficient training, good compression, and accurate reconstruction.

Figure 5: CMS latent space visualised in two dimensions via (a) t-SNE dimensionality reduction (b) TriMap dimensionality reduction.

The CMS AE LS was also visualised using both t-SNE and TriMap, as seen in Figure 5. This is a reduction from 15 dimensions to 2. t-SNE has created some clusters, as expected (see t-SNE on MNIST in Figure 12 for example of typical t-SNE cluster). TriMap also seems to be implying some sort of clustering of points. This demonstrates some classification of data may have occurred in the AE. TriMap generally is more successful in identifying hierarchies in the data as well as the underlying structure [26] so this is likely to be a more accurate representation of the LS. It could be a classification like this that incorrectly creates extra data, as seen in the mass distribution. Interestingly, both t-SNE and TriMap visualisations seem to have created what could be argued as 4 distinct clusters. In TriMap, these are stacked vertically on top of each other, slightly overlapping, whereas in t-SNE they are those separated clearly with blank space (that looks like rivers passing through land). This could affirm that 4 classes have been identified by the AE. It also gives more confidence to the idea that the AE may be using fewer than 15 dimensions for storing important information for reconstruction, influenced the sparsity constraint. The question is whether this sparsity is helping or harming reconstruction quality. It would be useful to compare

these reconstructions and LS to a set with a lower, or even zero valued, regularization parameter value, to see whether more dimensions are used. However, this was not done as the CMS AE is not the main focus for LS visualisation or optimisation. Again, these are all rough, qualitative observations; it is challenging to make any firm conclusions without labels.

4.2 Baler on CFD

The CFD set is used to "calibrate" the image AE, and demonstrate that it can be very effective on image data. Thus, only reconstruction quality will be discussed for this dataset. Several runs of training were conducted, gradually increasing duration when it was affirmed that everything was in working order. The run judged most successful (by loss and reconstruction quality) was run for 6000 epochs with BS 6000, β 0.001, and learning rate 0.002. A test size of 0.2% was set to be able to observe the validation loss alongside the training loss, to confirm that the model was not overfitting the data. 6000 epochs seems to have been a good point to stop training, as training further after a good fit can lead to overfitting. As seen in Figure 6(a), the training loss has significantly reduced and flattened. The initial large drop in loss indicates good selection of hyperparameters. The step like drops could be a reflection of a repetitive dataset [39], as the CFD images can look similar to one another. However, after the few steps seen in the first 500 epochs, the plot smooths showing that the model has learned more variations in the data. The validation loss decreases steadily along with the training loss and does not increase in the later epochs, indicating that the model has not overfit the data. The fact that the validation loss is slightly lower than the training loss is due to the fact that validation loss does not include the L_1 regularisation (Eqn. 3) in its loss calculation, but only the MSE loss (Eqn. 4). In the comparison

Figure 6: CFD Results. (a) Shows the loss plot of training the "CFD dense AE" for 6000 epochs with CR 100 and a legend including all other relevant parameters. The loss is on a log scale on the y-axis and the x-axis displays epochs. (b) Shows three of the image reconstructions (middle column) along with the original images (left column) and the residuals (difference) in the right column. The colorbar indicates the velocity in m/s .

of reconstructed images to original ones in Figure 6(b), the differences seen are minimal. All the pixel values in the difference plot (which shows the residuals) are close to zero, never going above 0.5. Most variation is seen in the "tail-end" of the slower blob, which varies most throughout the images. The model has a less concise basis to train on due to this variation. Overall this dataset gives a good example of the Baler dense AE working effectively on image data.

4.3 Baler on LArIAT

4.3.1 Training and Reconstruction Results

The training (using the dense AE), compression and reconstruction process for LArIAT was performed by Samuel Hill, who shared the reconstructions, loss plots, and compressed files with me. The hyperparameters were kept the same as for CFD initially (BS set to 6000, regularization parameter 0.001, learning rate 0.001). The model was able to train for no more than 2000 epochs,

rather than 6000, because it was noticed that the computer used was having trouble running for longer than this, as it was much more computationally intensive than the CFD dataset (the image size is much larger). The learning rate was increased to 0.005 in order to speed up the training, the plot of this loss is seen in the top half of Figure 7(a). This helped the loss drop a bit faster, however the curve was less smooth. There is still room for optimisation here. Compared to Figure 6(a), the loss has not flattened entirely; if training were increased, reductions in the loss would likely be seen. The bottom plot of Figure 7(a) shows the loss of training the dense AE on LArIAT with an increased CR of 548 as well as inclusion of validation loss, a learning rate of 0.001, and a training period of 2000 epochs (it was trained for longer since a more constrained LS makes reconstruction more challenging). This was done for LS visualisation (detailed and justified in Section 4.3.2). The validation loss is far lower than the training loss, again due to the L_1 term not being included. The loss seems to have plateaued more, as expected for longer training; however, note the difference in scale of the y-axis between the two plots, which limits the visibility of potential steps or irregularities in the loss of the model trained for 2000 epochs.

The reconstruction quality of this model was qualitatively poor; some examples are seen in Figure 7(b). In the top image, of the π^+ , the reconstruction is blurry and does not include the bend in the line seen in the original. The electron reconstruction (middle) is also blurry to the point that no physics could be inferred from the image. The photon reconstruction seems to be slightly better, even though also blurred. This blurring is typical of AE reconstructions. It blurriness was investigated further and it was found that a contributor to the blurriness can be using MSE loss. Large errors are emphasized due to the squaring of values (see Eqn. 4), while smaller errors are not as important [40], they could actually be made even smaller. Thus creating a general blur around where the original signal is, to the autoencoder, means low MSE value i.e., good reconstruction. This was not an issue for the CFD dataset, since it does not contain distinct line signals, but rather contains blurred boundaries itself. An improvement could be using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) [41] instead of MSE. This takes the absolute value of the difference between prediction and actual value, rather than squaring the two. This preserves the error more literally, not weighing larger errors as more important nor diminishing small errors. The L1 regularisation may also be damaging to the reconstruction quality. While it is important to prevent overfitting, an AE that is too sparse may be losing information about important features, or prioritising some features while smoothing out others, aided by the MSE loss. There is a trade-off between sparsity and local detail. Evident in 7(a), by the low validation loss, the regularization term has a large contribution to the total loss. A reason for this is the large amount of "background" in these images, likely weighted as low. This could be adjusted by decreasing β closer to zero.

Furthermore, a common theme in all the reconstructions is the added background signal, which looks like added texture in the background. With the appearance it has and how similar it looks in the three images, one could argue that a general average of all the signals has been "overlayed" onto the background of each reconstruction, to balance out the MSE loss. A solution in the right direction could be to separate the "foreground" (signal) and the background and make specific loss functions for both of these. However, one would have to come up with a reasonable cut-off metric to separate these two, which could result in some signals being lost to the background, that potentially contain important physical information.

This AE has also not been given enough data to train on. There is only 100 images of each particle type. While this may seem like much, especially considering the CFD dataset only contained 60 images, since there is not much signal to train on in each image, the AE is working with minimal information about how to encode features. It is already clear that the images with more signal reconstruct slightly better, as seen by the showers in the electron and photon images of Figure 7(b). The signal, while slightly blurry, has been reconstructed far better than the π^+ ; significantly for the photon, which has the most information to train on.

Reconstructions using the suggested modifications for testing of these arguments needs to be done for some clearer conclusions.

4.3.2 Visualising LArIAT Latent Space

For potential answers about reconstruction quality, and directions for improvement, the LS was visualised. It could, for example, be that the AE has separated tracks and showers or managed to classify different particle types, and used the general class of particles to inform reconstruction. As this is a labeled dataset, any classification of particle types should be visible. The LS was visualised using TriMap. It was first visualised directly with CR 100, resulting in a latent layer size of 351. Then with increased CR and LS of 64 dimensions (mentioned in 4.3.1) was done to make it easier for TriMap to reduce the LS to 2D, and hopefully get a more accurate representation of the actual

Figure 7: LArIAT Results. (a) Shows the loss plot of training the "CFD dense AE" for 1000 epochs with CR 100, learning rate 0.005, and a legend including all other relevant parameters on the top (called the first run) and the loss after training for 2000 epochs with CR of 548 for a smaller LS and learning rate 0.001 on the bottom (called the second run). Validation loss is also included on the bottom figure. The loss is on the y-axis and the x-axis displays epochs. (b) Shows three of the image reconstructions (middle column) along with the original images (left column) and the residuals (difference) in the right column (these are from the standard configurations with increased learning rate run). The colourbar indicates the charge deposited. The top event is labeled as a π^+ , the middle as an e^- , and the bottom as a photon.

LS. The reconstruction quality of the second run was qualitatively the same as the first run, and thus not shown here. The visualisation of the two LSs for comparison is shown in Figure 8. The overall topology of the data appears similar between the two runs, even if distributed slightly differently. This is to be expected as the reconstructions were also qualitatively similar. One can see similar colours being grouped together in similar locations and ways. On these grounds, only further plots of the 64 dimensional LS will be shown and any qualitative conclusions drawn from comments on the 64 dimensional LS are very similar for the larger LS, but just not mentioned here to prevent repetition.

To highlight some further classification, certain classes were highlighted and/or grouped in Figure 9 based on the following observations. The most notable clustering is that of the electrons and positrons, seen in 9(a). This is reasonable because the images of these two particles have virtually the same signal. In the latent space, they have been pushed to the outer edges of the global cluster, and to either side. A peculiar point is that the electrons and positrons have been separated from one another. This is unexpected. Upon further investigation of the images, it was noted that all images containing electron signals are angled such that they go from bottom left to top right on the image (as seen in Figure 7(b)), whereas all positron signals mirror this. Based on this separation of the two, we can infer that the direction, angle, and potentially placement, of the track or shower influences how it is classified and most likely, as a consequence, its reconstruction. Orientation has also been shown to play a large role in learned embeddings by Chris Olah [42] where 'ones' from the MNIST dataset (see example in 4.4.2, Figure 10) were shown to be near each other if they were similar in angle of orientation (a '1' that is a straight vertical line was placed, in the LS, next to other '1's that were close to exactly vertical, whereas ones slanted to the right were placed further away to one side, and those slanted to the left to the other side). In the reconstruction, when reconstructing from a certain data-point in the LS, the AE seems to generalise all the information of nearby data-points which means sometimes some signal is added, blurred, or an average of two points is made into one causing a morphed signal. As an extension to the points made about Figure 9(a), Figure 9(b) shows electrons, positrons, photons, and π^0

Figure 8: LArIAT in Baler 2D Latent Space scatter plots, reduced to 2D via TriMap. Shows the latent space of the (a) run 1 model, with CR 100 and latent space size 351 and (b) run 2 model with CR 548 and latent space size 64. The different particle types are classed by colour, with a key including all the labels and corresponding colors. The x and y axes are the two latent space components; units are arbitrary.

Figure 9: LArIAT in Baler 2D Latent Space scatter plots with certain particle classes highlighted. The highlighted classes are: (a) e^- and e^+ , (b) e^- , e^+ , π^0 , and photons, (c) π^+ and π^- , (d) K^+ and K^- , (e) μ and michel electrons, and (d) μ . The axes are again the latent space components and are thus arbitrary.

highlighted. These classes were grouped together because all their images show what looks more shower-like signals. The more shower-like, the closer the points are to the outside of the LS.

The concern with embeddings split into classes is over-classification, resulting in a reconstruction that looks completely different to what is expected from such a particle. This can occur where clusters of different classes overlap and is observed in the π^+ reconstruction in Figure 7(b), but also in the reconstruction of π^- , K^+ , and K^- . These pairs were highlighted together in Figures 9(c) and 9(d), respectively. These images contain variable signals. In the LS, they are scattered throughout the center, reflecting this irregularity in features. Their reconstructions are

often blurry, with lower total signal than most other images or sometimes new signals, with no counterpart in the original image. New information has been added to the reconstruction based on information from nearby points in the LS. In the π^+ reconstruction in Figure 7(b), the bend in the path has been completely removed as well as the other signals, not on the main track/shower. Some clearer classification could most likely aid in the reconstruction of these images.

The μ and michel electron images contain the "cleanest" tracks (especially the μ images). In Figure 9(e) the muons and michel electrons are clustered more towards the centre of the latent space cluster, far away from the images with large showers, as expected. But michel electrons appear to have a veritable overlap with the more shower-heavy regions, and this is reflected by some ambiguity and/or strong blurriness in reconstruction. In Figure 9(f) the muon cluster is highlighted on its own. These points demonstrate the most vicinity to their nearest neighbours of any of the particle types in these Figures. They also contain the least background signal. This led to further investigation of the images, where it was found that almost all the muon images contained a track in the top left quadrant of the image, moving from bottom left to top right of the quadrant. This reaffirmed the effect of signal location and angle on reconstruction quality, which is evidently influenced by the LS classifications. To ameliorate this, a pre-processing in which signals are all oriented in the same direction and all images are cropped to include less of the background. This could slightly harm the particle classification capability of the AE, but could aid in reconstruction as it would create clusters of similar images, like seen in the muon cluster of the LS. Since this project has a focus on image reconstruction and not particle classification (and the labels would still be preserved), such a solution could improve performance. However this draws it the risk of excluding data that may potentially contain important physics.

4.4 Baler on MNIST

The MNIST dataset was used for two reasons. The first is to affirm, or give more confidence to, the comments made on the LArIAT LS and the effect of LS topology on reconstruction. The second is to perform a brief qualitative comparison of Baler's image AE with other dimensionality reduction tools. The second goal also helps draw out some shortcomings to reducing the LS down to 2D with dimensionality reduction tools, slightly re-framing some of the comments made on these bases. MNIST shares some qualities with the LArIAT data. Both consist of defined lines with a close to zero-valued background. The advantage of MNIST is that the classes are more clearly defined (and more clearly identifiable by humans), the overall dataset is bigger, and the images themselves are actually smaller. The images have been prepared to contain the handwritten digit in the centre of the 28x28 pixel square. This is similar to the potential amelioration suggested for LArIAT, of pre-processing the images to include less background, and focus on the signal itself.

4.4.1 Training and Image Reconstruction

Training on MNIST was done twice (after all the necessary calibration and tuning of parameters was decided). Once, called Run 1, with BS 6000, test size of 0.2, and a CR of 100, and the second time, Run 2, with a BS of 1000, test size 0.2, and a compression ratio of 192. The former was performed with the goal of best reconstruction quality, and the latter was done with the goal of obtaining a 2-dimensional latent space. As MNIST images are smaller, it is much more reasonable to compress them to 2D than it is LArIAT. The smaller BS for the second run was set due to concerns about computer capability (it proved much more intensive to compress into 2D). The performance of the two models is shown in Figure 10. Both models have a steady drop in training and validation loss as seen in Figures 10(a) and 10(c). There is a slight concern of overfitting for run 2 as the validation loss becomes larger than the training loss. But given that the validation loss does not increase again after decreasing, this is unlikely. Both runs seem to smooth out the appearance of some images, as seen in the '5' reconstruction in (Figs. 10(b) and 10(d)) and it seems that some background signal has been added to the openings of the '5', indicating it may have almost been mis-classified as an '8'. The bottom tail of the '1' has been straightened. Run 1 demonstrated somewhat better reconstruction quality than Run 2, as is highlighted by the mistaken reconstruction of a '4' as a '9' in Figure 10(d). These images will be commented on more in the following section, in the context of the LS.

4.4.2 Latent Space Visualisation

With CR=100 in Run 1, the LS was 8 dimensional. This was compressed to 2D using TriMap, the Run 2 LS was visualised directly. Both are found in Figure 11. The stark difference between how

Figure 10: MNIST in Baler results of. Loss plots (a) run with CR=100, BS=6000, and standard hyperparameters (Run 1) and (c) run with CR=392, BS=1000, and standard hyperparameters (Run 2), along with corresponding image reconstructions (bottom row) along with original images (top images) for (b) Run 1 and (d) Run 2.

Figure 11: Latent space visualisation of MNIST through Baler image AE. Left is Run 1, with CR=100 and 8-dimensional latent space, reduced to 2-dimensional via TriMap. Right is the LS of Run 2, CR=392, with 2-dimensional latent space. A key for all the number colors is included in the top right. Axes are the latent space dimensions, with arbitrary units.

the points are spread out in the two figures demonstrated the difference that a further reduction via TriMap can have on the topology of the data. Similarities are the general cluster groupings and they relations to one another. '3', '5', and '8' are close together, even overlapping, with the clusters of '2' and '6' nearby; and the clusters of '4', '6', and '9' are near each other, on the opposite side of the LS. One noticeable difference is the '1'. TriMap has separated the '1' cluster out far from all the other clusters whereas in Run 2, Baler has placed the ones centrally, even wedged between two clusters of '8'. The limitation of the conclusions that have been previously drawn from LS must be acknowledged following this comparison. While they do inform image reconstruction quality, overall statements about the LS when reduced by other dimensionality reductions must be limited.

Focusing on Run 2, the cluster of '4' and '9' are overlapping with each other, justifying the false reconstruction of a '4' as a '9' in Figure 10(d). And since the cluster of '5' is overlapping with

Figure 12: Visualisation of MNIST being reduced into 2 dimensions using alternative dimensionality reduction techniques. Left: using TriMap directly, middle: using t-SNE, right: using PCA. Axes are again latent space dimensions, with arbitrary units. Legend indicating numbers is in the top right corner of the Figure.

the '8' cluster, the added background in the reconstruction of the '5' is justified, the '5' must come from one of these points within the '8' cluster. Many more inferences like this can be drawn when comparing the latent space with the image reconstructions, reaffirming the fact that classification influences reconstruction quality. If the classification can influence the reconstruction quality in this way, it could be helpful to encourage the model to place the embedded points far away from each other, such that the different data types are more separate and mis-reconstructions based on generalisation from nearby points are fewer, like seen in the Run 1, where TriMap has enforced a stronger separation of different number types. This can be done by modifications to the loss.

Some studies have shown that manipulation of properties in LS can influence reconstruction [19], as has been demonstrated here. Figure 12 shows how MNIST dimensionality is reduced by t-SNE, TriMap, and PCA. This can indicate what type of algorithms could be implemented in loss function to improve reconstruction quality. For a dataset like LArIAT, a triplet method combined with PCA like that of TriMap could be used. It maintains some semantic features about the different images, but makes distinct clusters. This could lead to a balance between using classification for informed reconstruction and preventing mis-classification from influencing reconstruction. If our data classes are very different, a t-SNE-like algorithm could be implemented. Whereas, if the classes are more similar and the data more continuous, PCA could be used (or just the standard AE as demonstrated in 4.2).

5 Conclusion and Outlook

This research project has three central conclusions. The first is that using machine learning for data compression is an extremely versatile tool that, when understood well and designed for specific data, can efficiently compress data and accurately reconstruct it. The second is that the loss function is essential to reconstruction quality of image data, and needs to be picked with the considerations of the features in the images. I suggest trying alternative loss functions for the various datasets, namely MAE, and a triplet method like that of TriMap. The third conclusion is that the latent space can be informative for shortcomings in reconstruction quality, and the reconstruction quality can be largely contingent on accurate classification. Thus, in order to improve reconstruction quality, one must improve classification. Again the loss function could be modified here. Alternatively, this could be done by using a convolutional autoencoder (CAE), which adds convolutional layers between hidden layers. This was used by the Baler collaboration in the past on the CFD dataset [11]. A convolutional layer essentially passes or 'convolves' a 'filter' over sub-regions of the input [43]. These filters can capture various features such as edges. The main advantage is that, since the filter is smaller than the total data, a convolutional layer is good at capturing local features. This is sometimes followed by a pooling layer to reduce complexity. Capturing local features more effectively could mean less blurry lines for both the LArIAT and MNIST dataset and more accurately classified embedding in the LS (more accurate relative to the actual particle labels, that it). Z. Cheng et al. used a convolutional autoencoder for image compression in [44] and showed it to outperform other models.

Three shortcomings of this project, apart from the limitation of dimensionality reduction for visualising LS, are highlighted. First, having limited computational power (working on my personal

computer, using a Central Processing Unit (CPU)) limited the capability of model training. Due to the long duration of training and for concern of damaging the CPU, it was often not possible to try and improve a model by adjusting the hyperparameters or to train models as long as desired. This could be improved by the use of a General Processing Unit (GPU). This is common in training machine learning models (it was, for example done, in the original Baler training on CMS [11]). Using a GPU could also meant enable use of the entire LArIAT dataset for training, rather than the subset of 2500 images. A larger dataset could give improved reconstruction quality as more features of individual particle types can be learned. When comparing MNIST reconstructions to LArIAT, MNIST clearly shows better results overall; this is largely due to the different sizes of the two training sets. The final shortcoming which makes the results of the project limited is that, apart from validation loss, which was shown to be an inaccurate measure at times (as it uses MSE), there was no overall metric for image reconstruction quality; only qualitative comments made from human observations. Residuals distributions, like those in CMS, could in future be implemented into the 2D AE model for a more reliable measure of reconstruction quality. This can also help pinpoint is certain particle types are reconstructing better than others, by making individual distributions for each particle type. A quantization of clustering in the LS could also be useful.

Using AEs for data compression is a prosperous field with much potential for versatile applications, contingent on customisation of the model to the data. For image compression in physics it poses a viable solution to the ever-growing storage problem. This project has shown that there is a clear path to optimising compression for good reconstruction, but for many datasets, many informed improvements need to be made. Placing more importance on image classification in LS embeddings, potentially with the use of a CAE for enhanced feature extraction, opens the door for using ANNs for particle type classification. In Adams et al. [21] this has already been performed using a convolutional neural network. This could be a potential future extension to the Baler software. Finally, with the addition of more customizable features, such as adding convolutional layers and personalising loss functions, the Baler AE, has the potential to be applicable to a vast array of image data. By optimising the image compression of more and more types of datasets, the Baler AE becomes applicable to not just physics, but countless disciplines. As already mentioned, data compression is an important topic in many disciplines and sectors, and Baler is one example of how Autoencoders have the potential of mitigating these problems.

References

- [1] T. Liu, J. Wang, Q. Liu, S. Alibhai, T. Lu and X. He, *High-ratio lossy compression: Exploring the autoencoder to compress scientific data*, *IEEE Transactions on Big Data* **9** (2023) 22.
- [2] E. Deelman, G. Singh, M. Livny, B. Berriman and J. Good, *The cost of doing science on the cloud: The montage example*, in *SC '08: Proceedings of the 2008 ACM/IEEE Conference on Supercomputing*, pp. 1–12, 2008, DOI.
- [3] ATLAS collaboration, *ATLAS Software and Computing HL-LHC Roadmap*, Tech. Rep. , CERN, Geneva (2022).
- [4] A.F. Heavens, E. Sellentin and A.H. Jaffe, *Extreme data compression while searching for new physics*, *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* **498** (2020) 3440–3451.
- [5] K. Albertsson, P. Altoe, D. Anderson, M. Andrews, J.P.A. Espinosa, A. Aurisano et al., *Machine learning in high energy physics community white paper*, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **1085** (2018) 022008.
- [6] C.O. Software and Computing, *CMS Phase-2 Computing Model: Update Document*, Tech. Rep. , CERN, Geneva (2022).
- [7] L. Posani, A. Paccioia and M. Moschettini, *The carbon footprint of distributed cloud storage*, 2019.
- [8] R. Acciarri, C. Adams, J. Asaadi, M. Backfish, W. Badgett, B. Baller et al., *The liquid argon in a testbeam (lariat) experiment*, *Journal of Instrumentation* **15** (2020) P04026–P04026.
- [9] C. Collaboration, S. Chatrchyan, G. Hmayakyan, V. Khachatryan, A. Sirunyan, W. Adam et al., *The cms experiment at the cern lhc*, *Jinst* **3** (2008) S08004.
- [10] C. Patauner, *Verlustbehaftete und verlustlose Datenkomprimierung für Daten von Hochenergiephysik Experimenten*, Ph.D. thesis, Graz, Tech. U., 2011.
- [11] F. Bengtsson, C. Doglioni, P.A. Ekman, A. Gallén, P. Jawahar, A. Orucevic-Alagic et al., *Baler – machine learning based compression of scientific data*, 2023.
- [12] J. Hussain, *Deep learning black box problem*, 2019.
- [13] V. Hedges, *Cells of the nervous system: The neuron*, in *Introduction to Neuroscience*, Michigan State University Libraries (22).
- [14] B. Xu, N. Wang, T. Chen and M. Li, *Empirical evaluation of rectified activations in convolutional network*, 2015.
- [15] A.L. Maas, *Rectifier nonlinearities improve neural network acoustic models*, 2013, <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:16489696>.
- [16] S. Singh, D.S. Singh and S. Kumar, *Modified mean square error algorithm with reduced cost of training and simulation time for character recognition in backpropagation neural network*, in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Frontiers of Intelligent Computing: Theory and Applications (FICTA) 2013*, S.C. Satapathy, S.K. Udgata and B.N. Biswal, eds., (Cham), pp. 137–145, Springer International Publishing, 2014.
- [17] D.E. Rumelhart, G.E. Hinton and R.J. Williams, *Learning internal representations by error propagation*, in *Parallel Distributed Processing: Explorations in the Microstructure of Cognition, Vol. 1: Foundations*, (Cambridge, MA, USA), p. 318–362, MIT Press (1986).
- [18] Y. Song, S. Hyun and Y.-G. Cheong, *A systematic approach to building autoencoders for intrusion detection*, in *Silicon Valley Cybersecurity Conference*, Y. Park, D. Jadav and T. Austin, eds., (Cham), pp. 188–204, Springer International Publishing, 2021.
- [19] Y. Liu, E. Jun, Q. Li and J. Heer, *Latent space cartography: Visual analysis of vector space embeddings*, *Computer Graphics Forum* **38** (2019) 67.
- [20] B.R. Martin and G. Shaw, *Quark dynamics: the strong interaction*, in *Nuclear and Particle Physics: An Introduction*, pp. 185–229, John Wiley Sons Ltd (2019).

- [21] C. Adams, M. Alrashed, R. An, J. Anthony, J. Asaadi, A. Ashkenazi et al., *Deep neural network for pixel-level electromagnetic particle identification in the microboone liquid argon time projection chamber*, *Physical Review D* **99** (2019) .
- [22] K. Pearson, *Liii. on lines and planes of closest fit to systems of points in space*, *The London, Edinburgh, and Dublin Philosophical Magazine and Journal of Science* **2** (1901) 559.
- [23] I.T. Jolliffe and J. Cadima, *Principal component analysis: a review and recent developments*, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences* **374** (2016) 20150202.
- [24] L. van der Maaten and G. Hinton, *Visualizing data using t-sne*, *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **9** (2008) 2579.
- [25] S. Kullback and R.A. Leibler, *On information and sufficiency*, *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics* **22** (1951) 79.
- [26] E. Amid and M.K. Warmuth, *Trimap: Large-scale dimensionality reduction using triplets*, 2022.
- [27] CMS collaboration, *Jetht primary dataset in aod format from run of 2012*, Tech. Rep. , CERN Open Data Portal (2017), DOI.
- [28] I. Nutini and on behalf of the LARIAT Collaboration, *The lariat experiment at fermilab*, *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **689** (2016) 012020.
- [29] LARIAT collaboration, M.G.M. Alves, “Lariat dataset.” Personal Communication, 2023.
- [30] Y. LeCun, C. Cortes and C.J.C. Burges. <http://yann.lecun.com/exdb/mnist/>.
- [31] “Pytorch.” <https://pytorch.org>.
- [32] R. Tibshirani, *Regression shrinkage and selection via the lasso*, *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)* **58** (1996) 267.
- [33] D.P. Kingma and J. Ba, *Adam: A method for stochastic optimization*, 2017.
- [34] “Scikit learn.” <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/install.html>.
- [35] HOLOVITZ CONTRIBUTORS collaboration, “Datashader.” <https://datashader.org/index.html>, 2023.
- [36] J.D. Hunter, *Matplotlib: A 2d graphics environment*, *Computing in Science & Engineering* **9** (2007) 90.
- [37] S.J. Wetzel, *Unsupervised learning of phase transitions: From principal component analysis to variational autoencoders*, *Physical Review E* **96** (2017) .
- [38] E. Trunz, M. Weinmann, S. Merzbach and R. Klein, *Efficient structuring of the latent space for controllable data reconstruction and compression*, *Graphics and Visual Computing* **7** (2022) 200059.
- [39] Google for Developers, “Interpreting loss curves.” <https://developers.google.com/machine-learning/testing-debugging/metrics/interpretic>.
- [40] J. Johnson, A. Alahi and L. Fei-Fei, *Perceptual losses for real-time style transfer and super-resolution*, 2016.
- [41] C.J. Willmott and K. Matsuura, *Advantages of the mean absolute error (mae) over the root mean square error (rmse) in assessing average model performance*, *Climate Research* **30** (2005) 79.
- [42] C. Olah, “Visualizing mnist.” <https://colah.github.io/posts/2014-10-Visualizing-MNIST/>, 2014.
- [43] Z.-H. Zhou, *Neural networks*, in *Machine Learning*, (Singapore), pp. 103–128, Springer Singapore (2021), DOI.
- [44] Z. Cheng, H. Sun, M. Takeuchi and J. Katto, *Deep convolutional autoencoder-based lossy image compression*, 2018.